

was stable for at least 24 hr. Beyond this time it showed slow degradation.

The effect of several ions on the extraction of lead was studied. The tolerance limit was calculated as described earlier^{1,2}. The results are given in Table.

TABLE — EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Pb (II) = 24.2 μg ; pH = 8.8; 0.001 M SBA in benzene
Tolerance limit μg Other ions present

2.0×10^4	Li^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , CN^- , acetate ⁻ , malonate ²⁻ , NO_3^-
1.5×10^4	Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$
1×10^4	Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Br^- , F^- , NO_2^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, SCN^- , thiourea, $\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}^{4-}$, WO_4^{2-}
4×10^3	VO_2^+ , SeO_4^{2-}
2×10^3	Pt^{4+} , Ir^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , TeO_3^{2-} , SO_3^{2-}
1×10^3	Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , $\text{Pd}^{2+(a)}$, Ce^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , Al^{3+}
5×10^2	$\text{Ag}^{+(e)}$, $\text{Hg}^{2+(e)}$, $\text{Cu}^{2+(b)}$, Rh^{3+} , Au^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Be^{2+} , $\text{Co}^{2+(c)}$, $\text{Ni}^{2+(d)}$
2×10^2	Tl^+ , Cd^{2+} , Ru^{3+} , $\text{Zn}^{2+(e)}$, tart ²⁻
1×10^2	Mn^{2+} , cit ³⁻

Selectively extracted with^{1,2} (a) 8-hydroxyquinoline, (b) acetyl-acetone, (c) 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, (d) dimethylglyoxime and (e) masked with alkalicyanide.

Application to the Analysis of Alloys Containing Lead

Lead was determined from the alloys such as gun-metal, solder and TMS alloys by the following procedure. About 0.1 g of the alloy was dissolved in 10 ml of concentrated nitric acid and the tin which was precipitated as metastannic acid was removed and determined gravimetrically. The filtrate and washings were made to 250 ml. A known aliquot of solution was taken and in case copper (II) was present, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5 and copper was removed by selective extraction with 3×10 ml of 0.1 M acetylacetone in benzene. The aqueous phase after the separation of copper containing lead and other ions like zinc and antimony was taken. Zinc was masked with alkalicyanide and the pH of the solution was adjusted to pH 8.5-9.1 to form negatively charged unextractable complexes. Lead (II) was extracted with 10 ml of 1×10^{-3} M benzene and was determined at 390 nm as usual. Antimony (III), if present is not extracted along with lead and therefore does not interfere. The results showed that the recovery of lead in gunmetal was 5.8% and 5.95% against 6.0%. In solder lead was 53.5% and 54.7% as against 55.0% and in TMS alloy lead was 85.0% and 83.3% against 84.6%.

The absorbance of the complex from 20 determinations with 48.8 μg of lead was 0.420 ± 0.010 . The relative standard deviation was $\pm 1.2\%$.

References

- O. B. MAHRE and E. B. SANDELL, *Talanta*, 1964, 11, 295.
- A. M. BULGAKOVA and A. M. VOLKOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1960, 15, 591.
- J. J. WARR and F. CULTITTA, *U. S. Geol. Surv. Profess.*, 1960 Paper No. 400B, 483; *A.A.*, 1961, 8, 2347.
- S. MUKHERJEE, H. K. SAHA and T. CHAKRABARTY, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1974, 269, 122.
- A. A. YADAV and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Talanta*, 1971, 18, 833.
- H. M. N. H. IRVING and A. H. NABILSI, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1968, 41, 505.
- J. STARY and E. HLADKY, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1963, 28, 227.
- V. M. SHINDE and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1967, 1785.
- S. B. AKKI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1972, 45, 167.
- R. R. MULYB and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Chemia. Analt (in press)*.
- M. V. R. MURTI and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 455.
- A. K. DE, S. M. KHOPKAR and R. A. CHALMERS, *Solvent Extraction of Metals*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, London, 1970.

Kinetics of Substitution of Mono(Oxalato)Tetra-aquochromium(III) Ion by Orthophosphoric Acid

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IT is observed that the oxalato-complexes of chromium (III) undergo substitution with orthophosphoric acid^{1,2}. In the present communication we report our results obtained in the substitution of mono(oxalato)tetraaquochromium (III) ion by orthophosphoric acid which is relatively faster than the substitution of tris(oxalato)-chromate (III).

Mono(oxalato)tetraaquochromium (III) perchlorate was prepared³, the procedure of which is described here briefly. Equimolar quantities of hexaaquochromium(II) perchlorate and reagent grade sodium oxalate were mixed and kept at 50° for several days. The reaction mixture containing $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^+$ is then adsorbed on a Dowex 50W $\times$ 8 (50-100 mesh) cation exchange resin. It was then selectively eluted from the column with 0.05 M perchloric acid after thoroughly washing the column with double distilled water. The purity of

the solution was checked by analysis for chromium and oxalate. The ratio of oxalate to chromium was found to be 1.03. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Ionic strength was kept at 3.0 with sodium nitrate. The rate of the reaction was followed with a Unicam SP600 spectrophotometer at 560 nm where the reactant mono-(oxalato)tetraaquochromium(III) has got an absorption maximum. The rate of the reaction was followed as a function of the metal complex, phosphoric acid and added oxalate concentrations as well as ionic strength.

In the substitution of tris (oxalato)chromate (III) by orthophosphoric acid the rate of the reaction was found to be retarded by the products and initial rate methods were employed for the evaluation of the rate constants. To verify the possibility of the effect of the products on the course of the reaction the order of the reaction with respect to time (n_t) as well as the order with respect to concentration (n_c) are evaluated. The value of n_t (3.40) was found to be greater than n_c (1.02) indicating the inhibition of the reaction rate by the product⁴. Hence initial rate methods were employed to evaluate the rate constants by the method described by Laidler⁴. An increase in the concentration of phosphoric acid increases the rate constant. The order of the reaction with respect to metal complex is found to unity. It is observed that an increase in the ionic strength decreases the rate constant indicating that the reaction is between ions of opposite sign. To verify the possibility of substitution of oxalate by phosphoric acid, the rate of the reaction was followed by variation of the added oxalate concentration. A decrease in the rate constant was observed with the increase in oxalate concentration. To find out the nature of the product species ion-exchange studies were carried out. The results indicated that the species is neither cationic nor anionic phosphato complex. This suggests that the product species may be neutral probably of the type $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)(\text{HPO}_4)^5$. This was further supported by our electrophoresis studies in which there was no movement of the spot on either side of the electrodes. The absorption spectrum of the product was found to be identical with that of the product obtained in the substitution of $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3^{3-}$ by phosphoric acid with two broad absorption peaks in the wavelength regions 430nm–450nm and 580nm–610nm. Results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The following mechanism is suggested to account for the experimental observations.

TABLE 1

Temperature = 28.5 ± 0.1 °C		Ionic Strength (μ) = 3.0	
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^+]$ (M)	$[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]$ (M)	10^3 Initial Rate moles lit ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	Pseudo first order rate constant, k min ⁻¹
0.001	3.0	0.38	3.80
0.002	3.0	0.81	4.05
0.003	3.0	1.18	3.93
0.004	3.0	1.54	3.85
0.005	3.0	1.86	3.72
0.006	3.0	2.38	3.97
0.004	1.0	0.61	1.53
0.004	2.0	1.13	2.83
0.004	2.5	1.38	3.45
0.004	3.5	2.01	5.03
0.004	4.0	2.27	5.68
0.004	3.0	2.13*	5.32*
0.004	3.0	1.83**	4.58**

* $\mu = 1.0$; ** $\mu = 2.0$

TABLE 2

Temperature = 28.5 ± 0.1 °C		Ionic Strength (μ) = 3.0	
[Oxalate] (M)	10^3 Initial Rate moles lit ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	Pseudo first order rate constant, k min ⁻¹	
0.002	1.32	3.33	
0.004	1.10	2.75	
0.006	0.93	2.33	
0.008	0.71	1.78	
0.010	0.58	1.45	

$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^+] = 0.004 \text{ M}$; $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4] = 3.0 \text{ M}$

Using the steady state concentration of the intermediate the rate equation is $-\frac{d[\text{O}]}{dt} = k K_1 K_2 [\text{C}][\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2 [\text{OXH}_2]^{-1}$ where C represents metal complex and K_1 and K_2 are k_1/k_{-1} and k_2/k_{-2} respectively. A plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4]^2$ gave a straight line with unit slope. A straight line with slope equal to -1 was obtained when k_{obs} is plotted against $1/[\text{OXH}_2]$. These observations are in agreement with the rate law suggested.

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References

1. V. M. RAO, V. ANANTA RAMAM, and M. N. SASTRI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45, 451.
2. N. R. ANIFINDI, V. M. RAO and V. ANANTA RAMAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 561.
3. T. SPINNER and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 1067.
4. KEITH J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics" Ch. 1. McGraw Hill, II Ed., 1965, p. 16.
5. R. F. JAMESON and J. E. SALMON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 360.

Viscosity Variations in Non-ideal Homogeneous Binary Liquid Mixtures of Non-electrolytes

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THE existence of new species in non-ideal homogeneous binary liquid mixtures of non-electrolytes have been predicted from viscosity measurements by various workers^{1,2} in the past. Recently, the authors in an earlier publication³ explained the occurrence of maxima or minima in the excess viscosity η^E versus composition plots of a few such systems by assuming the existence of mobile liquid structures having a central molecule of one component surrounded by the molecules of the other component. It was considered desirable to test the applicability of the authors' earlier conclusions further by considering some more systems in the hope to understand the deviations from ideal viscometric behaviour in terms of the molecular and bulk properties of the pure components.

Results and Discussion

In a homogeneous binary liquid mixture of components A and B, A provides the central molecule in corresponding liquid structures if $(X_A)_{max} \leq 0.5$ and surrounding molecules if $(X_A)_{max} \geq 0.5$ while either of the two situations are equally possible if $(X_A)_{max} = 0.5$, where $(X_A)_{max}$ the mole fraction of component A corresponds to $(\eta^E)_{max}$, the maximum excess viscosity of the binary³. Also for polar-polar and polar-apolar binaries, $\eta^E = +ve$ when $(\mu_c - \mu_s) = +ve$ and $\eta^E = -ve$ when $(\mu_c - \mu_s) = -ve$ where μ_c and μ_s are the dipole moments of the molecules of the central and surrounding components respectively forming the mobile liquid structures. On the other hand, for apolar-apolar

binaries, $\eta^E = +ve$ or $-ve$ according as the central molecule in the mobile liquid structures increases or decreases orientation in the mixture.

In order to verify the above conclusions, the viscosity of various binary liquid mixtures of non-electrolytes at 25° and varying compositions were taken from published data⁴ and the excess viscosity η^E was calculated⁵ and plotted against X_A for each system. A close look at the curves so obtained made them to be grouped in three categories: (i) curves showing maxima alone, (ii) curves showing minima alone, and (iii) curves showing maxima and minima both. One typical curve from each category is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Plots of excess viscosity (η^E) versus mole fraction (X_A) for binary mixtures at 25°C of (I) CCl_4 (A) + CH_3OH (B) showing maxima alone, (II) $\text{CH}_2\text{CO-CH}_3$ (A) + $\eta\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7\text{CO}_2\text{H}$ (B) showing minima alone, & (III) CCl_4 (A) + $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (B) showing maxima and minima both.

For every system considered, the value of $(X_A)_{max}$ and the corresponding value of $(\eta^E)_{max}$ were obtained from the maxima/minima in the respective plots of η^E vs X_A . Further, the type of the central as well as the surrounding component and the sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ for polar-polar as well as polar-apolar binaries and orienting tendency of the central molecule of corresponding mobile liquid structure in apolar-apolar binaries were predicted by applying the above conditions. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

A close observation of table 1 indicates that for systems 1 to 17, the predicted sign of $(\mu_c - \mu_s)$ tallies with the calculated sign as required. However, for the

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